

GREEN CONSUMERS - WAYS TO DEVELOP GREEN GROWTH WITHIN A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT:

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The article discusses sustainable economic growth, green economy, its importance, depletion of natural resources, global warming problems, its prevention, the report highlights the importance of environmental protection, the effective use of clean and renewable energy, the increasing relevance of green production and consumption, and the tendency of consumers to adopt green consumption. In addition, it provides analysis and suggestions on green consumer behavior, consumption that is compatible with environmental protection for future generations, and consumers who prefer to purchase green products and reduce waste, and behaviors that improve environmental outcomes.

Introduction. Currently, sustainable growth and development are the main economic policies for countries around the world. The depletion of natural resources, the deepening of environmental pollution and global warming are the red alert problems of our planet. Every country on earth is responsible for protecting our planet. Therefore, increasing environmental awareness has brought about new trends in consumer behavior. Countries aim to improve their economic performance and quality of life through a green economy while not polluting or harming the environment. In addition, it aims to support personal sustainable development through sustainable consumption. In this context, this article analyzes and highlights the importance of sustainable consumption trends and the role of green consumers in the development of a green economy. In addition, developed countries

and developing countries are compared with each other through the results of the global ecological footprint.

Uzbekistan is also one of the leading countries in the region in implementing reforms in this area. The fact that several regulatory legal acts have even been adopted in the legislative system in this regard indicates that the state is not indifferent to the prospects of the sector. In particular, in accordance with Resolution No. PQ-4477 of October 4, 2019, the Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the transition to a "green" economy for the period 2019-2030 was approved. According to it, during this period, the following tasks have been set: to increase the share of renewable energy resources in total electricity needs to 25%, to form a single comprehensive development policy aimed at reducing transport costs and ensuring the effective operation of the transport sector, to develop "green" transport in accordance with long-term city development plans and environmental safety measures, to introduce a "green" lending and venture financing system.

Analysis of literature on the topic.

Researchers and practitioners have explored and proposed imperatives and implementation mechanisms for ensuring the sustainability of production-consumption systems. The literature review identified 11 main different approaches to creating sustainable production-consumption systems. (Lebel and Lorek, 2008).[1] Important incentives for strong sustainable consumption can come from social innovation. (Seifang and Smith, 2007; Seifang, 2009) [2] .The increasing relevance of green production and consumption can be attributed to its recognition as a high priority issue in the United Nations (2018) Sustainable Development Goals, which has brought green consumer research to the forefront.[3]The role of a green economy, sustainable consumption and production, and resource efficiency for sustainable development: Sustainable consumption and production focuses on improving production processes and consumption practices to reduce resource consumption, waste generation, and emissions throughout the entire life cycle of processes and products.[4]

Research methodology

The research mainly used scientific research methods such as statistical grouping, comparative scientific abstraction, that is, green economy, green consumers, sustainable consumption and production and resource efficiency, transition to a green economy The dynamics of green growth are presented and analyzed. Green growth is a solution to economic and environmental problems in the sustainable development of enterprises. Conclusions and proposals were developed to improve the sector.

Analysis and results

Green consumption is related to sustainable development or sustainable consumer behavior. It is a form of consumption that protects the environment for present and future generations. It defines responsibility or shared responsibility for solving environmental problems by consumers adopting environmentally friendly behavior, such as choosing organic products, using clean and renewable energy, and choosing products produced by companies with zero or near-zero impact. (zero waste, zero-emission cars, zero-energy buildings, etc.) [5]

Green consumption in Western societies emerged in the 1960s and early 1970s with growing awareness of the need to protect the environment and human health from the effects of industrial pollutants and economic and population growth. In the 1980s, the first American "green" brands began to emerge and explode in the American market. In the 1990s, green products gradually grew and became a phenomenon in their own right. American interest in green products began to grow again in the early 2000s and has continued to grow.[6]

A green consumer is a type of consumer who buys green products, such as eco-friendly, organic, or energy-efficient products, and therefore consumes fewer natural resources. A consumer who prefers sustainable consumption patterns, including consuming less, purchasing green products, and reducing waste. A person who has a consumer attitude towards preserving the environment. This refers to consumers who choose green products. A consumer who is sensitive to environmental protection when making purchasing decisions. A person who supports environmental causes and prefers green products. A type of consumer who is concerned with personal environmental and social needs.

He or she typically approaches the market in a way that penalizes profit maximization while ignoring the maximum satisfaction of consumer needs within environmental constraints and regulations. A person who is mindful of the environment in which he or she lives. The competitive market focuses on economic laws that require efficient use of limited resources to satisfy individual and social needs, while the market is regulated by authorities to encourage production so that the behavior of producers is less oriented towards maximizing profits and more focused on optimizing consumption and maximizing consumer needs within environmental constraints and regulations. A consumer who associates the act of purchasing or consuming products with the opportunity to protect the environment.

A green consumer is “someone who buys products and services that have a positive (or less negative) impact on the environment...” Green consumers act ethically, not only out of personal need but also out of respect. They consider the well-being of society as a whole and the environmental consequences (costs and benefits) of their personal consumption. Green consumers are more conscientious in their use of assets, for example, using their goods without wasting resources. However, the Eurobarometer Consumer Behaviour Survey (2013) showed that consumers are not interested in adopting a new set of behaviours that are more environmentally friendly. This report states that although a very large proportion of citizens (80%) buy green products, more than half are classified as occasional users (54%) and only a quarter are regular buyers of green products. Ordinary products (26%) are bought by people This suggests that most people do not consistently behave as green consumers, the main reason for this is probably due to social and economic constraints, such as green products being more expensive than non-green products or green products not always being easy to find. There are two types of consumers:

- preventive consumers who feel a moral obligation to a green lifestyle;
- types of consumers who focus more on their aspirations and dreams and do not feel strong pressure to quickly change their behavior in the direction of being environmentally friendly

What do we mean by green products? A green product is a product that is preferred by consumers because it helps protect the environment during the production, use, and disposal of the product. In general, organic, ecological, recyclable, and energy-efficient products are called green products.

Figure 1. Transition to a Green Economy between 2000 and 2015

From Figure 1, we can see that the material density of Asia and the Pacific is measured in domestic material consumption per dollar. A green economy is defined as one that is low-carbon, resource-efficient and socially inclusive. In a green economy, employment and income growth are achieved through public and private investment in economic activities, infrastructure and assets that reduce carbon emissions and pollution, increase energy and resource efficiency, and prevent the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services. Green investment should be enabled and supported through targeted public spending, policy reforms and changes in taxation and regulation.

Figure 2. Resource efficiency

The role of green economy, sustainable consumption and production and resource efficiency for sustainable development: Sustainable consumption and production focuses on improving production processes and consumption practices to reduce resource consumption, waste generation and emissions throughout the entire life cycle of processes and products. Efficiency refers to the ways in which resources are used to deliver value to society and aims to reduce the amount of resources required per unit of product or service, as well as the waste and emissions generated. A green economy provides a macroeconomic approach to sustainable economic growth, with a focus on investment, employment and skills.

Three main areas of current work on the green economy are:

1. Promote a macroeconomic approach for sustainable economic growth through regional, subregional and national forums.
2. Demonstrate Green Economy approaches with a focus on the use of green finance, technology and investment
3. Support countries in developing and mainstreaming macroeconomic policies to support the transition to a green economy.

Figure 2. Sustainable Consumption and Production

Multilateral cooperation to promote a green economy is supported to accelerate and strengthen sustainable changes in consumption and production patterns. In addition to governments and non-profit organizations, the UN Environment Agency has also strengthened cooperation with the private sector, which is a very important actor in promoting resource efficiency and a green economy. With clear conditions for economic growth, especially strong sustainable consumption, it is not in the short-term interests of powerful actors ([Fuchs, 2005](#)).[5]

Green growth means promoting economic growth and development while ensuring that natural resources continue to provide the resources and environmental services on which our well-being depends. To do this, it must catalyze: investments and innovations that ensure sustainable growth and generate new economic opportunities; a return to “business as usual” would be unwise and ultimately unsustainable, which could lead to risks; human costs and constraints on economic growth and development. This could lead to increased water scarcity, resource challenges, air and water pollution, climate change and irreversible loss of biodiversity; the need for strategies to achieve green growth.

Green growth has the potential to solve economic and environmental problems and unlock new resources [8]

Growth is achieved through the following channels:

- **Productivity.** Encouragement to improve the efficiency of resource and natural resource use: increasing productivity, reducing waste and energy consumption, and maximizing resource value.
- **Innovation.** Opportunities for innovation, policies and framework conditions that enable innovation, and ways to address environmental challenges.
- **New markets.** Creating new markets by stimulating demand for green technologies, goods and services; creating the potential for new jobs.
- **Confidence.** Increasing investor confidence through predictability and sustainability is what governments want to address key environmental challenges.
- **Stability.** Balanced macroeconomic conditions, reducing and sustaining resource price volatility. For example, fiscal consolidation by reviewing the composition and efficiency of public spending and raising revenues by pricing pollution. It can also reduce the risk of negative shocks to growth:
 - Resource constraints that make investment more expensive, such as the need for capital-intensive infrastructure (e.g. desalination plants) when water resources become scarce or their quality deteriorates. In this regard, the loss of natural capital may exceed the gains from economic activity and the ability to sustain future growth.
 - Imbalances in natural systems are also more profound, sudden, extremely damaging and potentially dangerous. irreversible impacts - as has happened to some fish stocks and could harm biodiversity under unabated climate change. Attempts to identify potential limits, in some cases - climate change, the global nitrogen cycle and biodiversity loss - have already been exceeded.

Conclusion and suggestions

The green growth strategy focuses on mutually reinforcing aspects of economic and environmental policies. It takes into account the full value of natural capital as a factor of production and its role in growth. It focuses on cost-effective ways to reduce environmental pressures to influence the transition to new forms of growth.

Green growth policies aim to close this gap and increase the returns to green investment and innovation. They also aim to manage any negative economic impacts on firms, while maintaining incentives to improve economic performance, while minimizing the distributional consequences of change for the most disadvantaged groups in society.

Implementing a green growth strategy involves a mix of tools drawn from two broad sets of policies. The first set includes the framework conditions that mutually reinforce economic growth and the preservation of natural capital. This includes key fiscal and regulatory settings, such as tax and competition policies, which, if well designed and implemented, maximize the efficient allocation of resources. This is a familiar economic agenda with the added understanding that policies can be good for both the environment and the economy. These settings should be complemented by innovative policies that prioritize the ingenuity needed if we are to harness natural capital more efficiently and effectively.

The second set includes policies aimed at promoting the efficient use of natural resources and making pollution more costly. They include a mix of price-based and other policy instruments. Annex 1 to this Report details a comprehensive set of green growth policy instruments that cover these two sets.

So, in developing green consumers-green growth within a sustainable economy:

- There needs to be a greater focus on investments and innovations that will ensure sustainable growth and create new economic opportunities.
- A return to “business as usual” would be unwise and ultimately unsustainable, which could lead to risks, in a green economy, transitioning to green businesses and producing green products using green investments;
- human costs and constraints on economic growth and development. This could lead to increased water scarcity, for which the transfer of processing technologies would be desirable.

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